

Zenodo replicate data

2.27.26

The data presented in the following figures already includes 3 biological replicates

Figure 2B
Figure 2D
Figure 3A
Figure 5D
Figure 6A
Figure 7C
Figure 7D
Figure S1A
Figure S1D
Figure S5
Figure S9

The data presented in the following figures already includes 5 biological replicates

Figure 5B
Figure 5C
Figure 6D
Figure 6E

Figure 2C biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

Figure 2E biological replicates

Figure 3B biological replicates

Figure 3C biological replicate 2

Figure 3C biological replicate 3

Figure 3D biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

Figure 4A biological replicates

Figure 4B biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

NOTE: Order of strains is different than in the published figure.

Figure 4C biological replicates

Figure 5A biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

Figure 5E biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

NOTE: Orientation of the biological replicate data is different than the published figure

Figure 6B additional biological replicate images

Figure 6C additional biological replicate data

n=122 cells

Figure 7A biological replicates

NOTE: Order of strains is different than in published figure

Figure 7B biological replicates

Rep 2:

Rep 3:

Figure S1B replicates

Note: Biological replicate 3 contains an additional strain ($\Delta pldA$) compared to published figure.

Figure S1C biological replicate 2

Figure S1C biological replicate 3

Figure S2A uncropped blots

Figure S2A biological replicate 2 uncropped blots

Figure S2A biological replicate 3 uncropped blots

Figure S2B uncropped blots

WT:

Δ *lpt*:

Δ *aas*:

Figure S2B biological replicate 2

Figure S2B biological replicate 2 uncropped blots

Figure S2B biological replicate 3

Figure S6 additional biological replicate images

Figure S7 biological replicates

